

Penta-Coordinated Base-adducts of *Bis*-(chloroacetoacetylanilido) Cu(II) with Nitrogen Donors

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA, S. K. PUJARI and A. CHIRANJEEVI

Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur, Orissa

Manuscript received 26 December 1980, revised 16 April 1981, accepted 19 May 1981

Five green crystalline compounds, having the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{B}]$, where *cl-acacN* is chloroacetoacetylanilide anion and *B* is a heterocyclic nitrogen donor like γ -picoline, β -picoline, pyridine, quinoline and piperidine have been characterised as penta-coordinated mono-adducts on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral data.

ATTEMPTS are being made to prepare complexes of rare coordination number using β -diketones, γ -substituted β -diketones, β -ketoesters and *o*-hydroxy aryl carbonyl compounds as chelating agents¹⁻³. Although complexation behaviour of β -diketones have been extensively studied⁴⁻⁷, very little is known about the chelating ability of γ -substituted acetoacetylanilide which closely resembles the β -diketones. Syamal and Dutta have reported⁸ hexa-coordinated complexes of nickel(II) *bis* acetoacetylamides with amines. We have earlier reported⁹⁻¹⁰ a number of penta-coordinated adducts of *bis*(chloro/bromo acetylacetonato) Cu(II) and Zn(II) with heterocyclic and aliphatic bases. This communication describes the monoadducts of copper(II) *bis* chloroacetoacetylanilide with different heterocyclic amines.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. *Bis* (acetoacetylanilido) Cu(II) was prepared by usual method. Dry chlorine gas was passed through the methanolic suspension of *bis* (acetoacetylanilido) Cu(II) till it dissolved and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand in an ice-bath when an olive green

compound separated out. This was filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Analysis of the compound indicated the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2]$. IR spectra provided the evidence for the formation of the chelate, $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2]$ requires C, 49.42; H, 4.11; N, 5.76%; found C, 49.16; H, 3.92; N, 5.48%. Adducts were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of the chelate with nitrogen donors in 1 : 2 ratio for about 2 hrs. On cooling overnight, light green to blue crystalline compounds separated which were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal was estimated by EDTA titration method, halogen by gravimetric method and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on solid specimen by Guoy method using $\text{Co}[\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. IR spectra were recorded in KBr using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in 10^{-3} *M* chloroform-base solution using Hilger-Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Analysis, conductance, magnetic moment and ir spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC MEASUREMENT AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	%Copper		%Nitrogen		μ_{eff} B.M.	Δ_M mhos cm^2	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.						
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2]$	15.08	15.22	3.31	3.35	1.75	7.8	1620	1575	1140	$\frac{430}{320}$ $\frac{440}{325}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\gamma\text{-pic}]$	12.27	12.45	5.43	5.48	1.82	7.5	1635	1585	1145	$\frac{435}{330}$ $\frac{435}{320}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\beta\text{-pic}]$	12.35	12.45	5.45	5.48	1.79	8.0	1640	1580	1145	$\frac{430}{330}$ $\frac{435}{320}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{Py}]$	12.69	12.80	5.59	5.63	1.84	10.0	1630	1580	1140	$\frac{435}{320}$ $\frac{435}{320}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{Q}]$	11.58	11.62	4.07	5.12	1.80	9.5	1635	1585	1145	$\frac{430}{320}$ $\frac{430}{325}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{Pip}]$	12.57	12.64	5.49	5.57	1.78	14.5	1640	1580	1150	$\frac{430}{325}$

γ -pic = γ -picoline, β -pic = β -picoline, Py = Pyridine, Q = Quinoline, Pip = Piperidine, *cl-acacN* = chloroacetoacetylanilide anion.

Results and Discussion

Copper(II) chelate and the base-adducts correspond to the formulae $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{B}]$ respectively, where cl-acacN is chloroacetoacetylanyl anion and B is a nitrogen donor ligand like γ -picoline, β -picoline, pyridine, quinoline or piperidine. Complexes are light green to blue in colour and have low melting points. The conductance of the complexes in acetone is very low (Δ_M being in the range of 7-14.5 mhos cm^2), indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic measurement show the complexes to be paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.78-1.84$ B.M.) with the presence of one unpaired electron.

IR spectra of the chelate, chlorochelate and the base-adducts are quite informative. Three bands appeared at 1650 cm^{-1} , 1590 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} in free ligand assignable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations. Decrease of these frequencies to lower frequency region is observed in case of metal chelate and chlorochelate. Disappearance of the bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ at 3060 cm^{-1} and $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ at 1220 cm^{-1} and appearance of a new band around 800 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$ vibration provide evidence for the formation of chlorochelate. Again, in case of base-adducts $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations have been observed to shift to higher frequency regions (in comparison to copper chelate and chlorochelate). Most of the absorption bands due to the heterocyclic bases have been modified in the base-adducts indicating their bonding to the copper(II) ion. The sharp band observed at 3300 cm^{-1} in the free ligand, copper chelate and base-adducts which can be assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ vibration, shows the non-coordination of this group to the metal ion. However, direct evidence of bonding of the ligands was obtained by the occurrence¹¹ of $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ and

$\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$ around 430 cm^{-1} and $\sim 320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively in the far ir spectra of these adducts.

$\text{Cu}(\text{acacN})_2$ gives a high intensity band at 240 nm ($\epsilon=20,100$) whereas in the chlorochelate the band shifts to 270 nm ($\epsilon=11,500$) as halogenation results in an increase of the π -electron delocalisation in the ring.

A single broad absorption band is observed for $[\text{Cu}(\text{cl-acacN})_2\text{B}]$ around 655 nm ($\epsilon=140$) in the visible region whereas in case of chlorochelate the band is around 665 nm ($\epsilon=105$). Though the band does not shift much on co-ordination with the base, there is an increase in the extinction coefficient. Gillard and Wilkinson⁶ have studied the absorption spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{acacN})_2\text{Q}]$ in dichloromethane and reported bands at 658 nm ($\epsilon=41$) and 650 nm ($\epsilon=71$) respectively.

These adducts are presumably pentacoordinated.

References

1. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, accepted.
2. N. C. MISHRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 24, 861.
3. N. C. MISHRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, **47**, 3, 81.
4. D. P. GRADDON and D. G. WEEDEN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **16**, 980.
5. D. P. GRADDON and D. G. WEEDEN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **17**, 607.
6. R. D. GILLARD and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1963, 639.
7. R. R. SINGH and R. SAHAI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 639.
8. A. SYAMAL and R. L. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1.
9. B. B. MAHAPATRA, B. K. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Communicated.
10. B. B. MAHAPATRA, N. C. MISHRA and S. GURU, *Acta Chimica (Hungary)*, Communicated.
11. J. R. FERRARO, "Low frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Intenum Press, New York, 1971.